

Relationship among Funding, Supply of Teaching-Learning Materials and Students' Academic Performance in Senior Public Secondary Schools in Borno State, Nigeria

Abdulkadir Mohammed Saidu

Department of Education, University of Maiduguri

msabdul@unimaid.edu.ng +2348032828413

Muhammad Waziri Bularafa

Department of Education, University of Maiduguri

Muhammad Ali Mustapha

Department of Education, University of Maiduguri

Abstract

Keywords:

Teaching
Learning
Resources,
Funding and
Students
Academic
Performance

Introduction

This study examined the relationship among funding, the supply of teaching and learning resources, and students' academic performance in senior secondary schools in Borno State, Nigeria.

Methodology

The study used a correlational research design. The target population was 17,229 teachers, from which 387 teachers were sampled using simple random sampling techniques. Data collection instruments included a questionnaire and a proforma. The questionnaire, named "Questionnaire on Funding, Teaching, Learning Materials, and Students' Academic Performance (QFTLMSAP)," was created using a 5-point Likert scale for teachers. The proforma was used to collect information on students' academic performance. The reliability of the questionnaire was assessed using the Cronbach Alpha technique, yielding an internal consistency estimate of 0.87. A Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was employed to determine the relationship between the variables.

Findings/Results

The study found that funding was significantly related to the provision of adequate teaching and learning resources. It also established that teaching and learning resources were significantly related to students' academic performance. The perceived funding level had a direct influence on learners' academic performance.

Conclusion

The study concluded that adequate funding and the proper utilization of teaching and learning resources in the instructional process are essential for realizing positive academic performance among learners.

Recommendations

The study recommended ensuring adequate funding and the consistent supply of teaching and learning resources, which should be effectively utilized in the instructional process to improve learners' academic performance.

Introduction

Education is a dominant factor in determining the socio-economic development in a country as it is the critical factor in religion, social, cultural, political and economic development of any nation. It is the foundation for training personnel to serve in various economic sectors of the country (John, 2019). According to National Policy on Education (2013) education is compulsory and a right of every Nigeria irrespective of gender, social status, religion, colour, ethnic background and any peculiar individual challenges. Education could be said to be fundamental right of every citizen in the country.

Allocating financial resources in education is a long-standing matter of dispute. Policymakers, educators, and communities are all concerned with the influence of school spending on the achievement of students. The allocation of educational resources by government and other stakeholders has a substantial impact on the quality of education and student outcomes. The impact of school financing on student accomplishment is numerous and complex. It includes not only the amount of financial resources but also how they are distributed and utilized. Researchers have long investigated how funding levels, resource distribution tactics, and environmental factors impact students' academic achievement.

Government support for secondary schools is critical to ensure that students have access to high-quality education. This financial assistance often covers a variety of critical factors, such as teacher wages, facility development, curriculum enhancement, and the provision of vital educational supplies (Antofina, 2016). Adequate finance allows schools to maintain a positive learning environment, hire experienced teachers, and offer a wide range of educational programs. Furthermore, government funding helps to

eliminate discrepancies between schools, encouraging fairness and ensuring that kids from different socioeconomic backgrounds have equal access to educational opportunities. Overall, investing in secondary education is an important approach for cultivating a well-educated and talented workforce, which contributes to a country's overall development and progress.

Government funding for teaching materials improves the overall learning experience by encouraging innovation and creativity in instructional methods. Teachers with access to a variety of materials can use a number of teaching approaches to accommodate different learning styles and preferences. This adaptability helps to create a more interesting and dynamic learning environment, encouraging a deeper grasp of the material being taught. Furthermore, government support for teaching and learning resources promotes educators' professional development. Teachers can stay up to date on educational trends, enhance their teaching skills, and adapt to changing curricula thanks to funding-supported training programs, workshops, and materials. This investment in teacher development benefits students by guaranteeing high-quality instruction (Ndhlovu, 2015).

The government is now the primary source of funding for education, as it is no longer perceived as a private enterprise. Prior to the government taking over schools, missionaries were the primary source of funding for education, particularly at missionary institutions. Currently, the federal government is responsible for funding education across the country. This is prevalent at all institutions nationwide. The federal government directly controls institutions like universities, polytechnics, colleges of education, and special schools. However, state and local governments pay for teacher training colleges, secondary schools and primary schools

respectively.

Experts in school finance recommend increasing the proportion of education revenue from the Federation account and relying on state and local governments for the remainder. The program should be tailored to each child's educational needs, taking into account local conditions and ensuring a fair distribution. Improving educational quality in one state benefits the overall national welfare due to population mobility. The Federal government's taxation power allows for sufficient revenue and equitable distribution of the tax burden. It is only with this level of federal spending will the significant gaps in wealth among states be overcome.

Education Cannot Wait (ECW) is a catalytic fund programme designed to transform the delivery of education for countries in emergencies and protracted crises. It provides support and funding to prioritize education at the onset of a crisis; joining up governments, humanitarian actors and development efforts to deliver education. ECW protects development funding by providing rapid emergency support, helps countries get back on track to longer-term planning and finance, while collaborating with organizations such as The Global Partnership for Education (GPE) to build resilience into education systems. Poor academic performance of students in public schools in Borno State has been attributed to inadequate of effective instructional media, funding, facilities and lack of qualified teachers (Anyadiegwu, 2018; Adebisi, Tewogbade & Olajide, 2017; Owolabi, 2012). This demand for satisfactory funding towards the provision of teaching learning resources was found to have a positive impact on students' academic performance based (Ufonabasi & Nsimeneabasi, 2020).

Adequate financing ensures that students have access to current textbooks, teaching

materials, and technology. This is critical for keeping curriculum content current and relevant, allowing students to gain the knowledge and skills required in a quickly changing environment. Furthermore, government funding contributes to reducing educational resource inequities between affluent and economically disadvantaged communities. According to Museba (2012), low-income schools frequently struggle to supply basic supplies, which impedes students' capacity to engage in effective learning. Governments may close the resource gap and create a more level playing field for all children, regardless of socioeconomic status, by distributing funds to schools according to need.

Corruption, on the other hand, is one of today's most serious issues. It undermines effective governance, fundamentally distorts public policy, results in resource misallocation, hinders the private sector and private sector development, and disproportionately affects the poor (Chanda, 2023). The government, through the ministry of education, is responsible for subsidizing schools so that they can function properly. These donations aid in the purchase of teaching and learning tools for a school. According to Antofina (2016), teaching materials are tools used by facilitators to assist them run a lesson efficiently. Oxfam (2011) stated that "financing for teaching and learning materials can have an impact on teaching and learning.

The education system in Nigeria has been characterized as examination oriented whereby passing of examinations are used as a gauged for determined the performance of an individual or organization (Reche, Bundi, Riungu and Mbugua (2012). This means that the significance of funding towards provision of teaching learning materials cannot be overemphasize. Scholars and stakeholders in education believes that funding is one of the determinants in provision of teaching learning

materials which significantly affect the students' academic performance.

Education remains the determinant for upward stratification, social and economic development of any nation but the Borno State government has not shown courageous commitment to the educational sector especially in area of manpower strength and development as well as supply of teaching learning resources. The manifestation could be seen in the low government funding on education, decaying and lack of functional infrastructure in public secondary schools which have led to demoralization of the teaching staff.

Studies conducted by various scholars have shown that funding affects students' academic performance in public schools, (Lumuli, 2009). World Bank (2012) and Education Cannot Wait (2021) concurs that depending on the framework and the perspective from which funding was required, under the right or abnormal conditions, increasing inputs that are in scarce supply and can lead to a high fringe return on the learning process.

The future of Borno State as a community depend in the quality of its education. Education remains the major instrument for individual socio-economic empowerment, national socio-economic development and growth as well as poverty reduction (Rowell & Money 2018). The Borno State Government at various levels (local and state) had made an attempt to improve the funding of educational sector over the year. In spite of the reforms carried out by the past and current government, there was little or no nothing on ground to inspire confidence in that very vital segment of our national economy (Rowell & Money 2018). Given the significant amount of government support to schools, there was no evidence of its impact on student academic performance. While some scholars in Borno State believed that money can improve pupils'

academic performance, others have found no meaningful benefit.

In spite of the recognition of education as a right, enrolment rates in secondary schools in Borno state public secondary declined from 25% in 2020 to 27% in 2023 with the most declines being realized in northern part of Borno State (UNICEF, 2023). These might be attributed to low funding of the sector, cultural belief, religion and insurgency activities which has devastated effect on personnel (teaching and non – teaching staff), instructional and infrastructural materials as well as students' academic performance. The developing countries which Nigeria is one has not responded effectively to the need to increasing funding in educational sector.

The secondary and other institutions of learning were in a state of decay with most of the institutions were underfunded, and teachers are underpaid. This has significantly affected education sector particularly teaching staff in the state to search for greener pastures in the sector that were prioritize or well-funded. Apart from the impact of inadequate funding on the quality of the teaching and learning process in our institute of education, student support is now inadequate (Uboglu, 2011).

Provision of quality and widespread education requires adequate provision of human resources (teaching and teaching staff) and physical resources such as classrooms, laboratories and libraries which are acquired through the availability of funding in schools (Ufonabasi & Nsimeneabasi, 2020). This indicates that funding is an important aspect in the provision of quality education. It's against this background that the researchers examined the relationship between funding, supply of teaching learning materials and students' academic performance in public senior secondary in Borno State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study were determined the;

1. relationship between funding and supply of teaching learning resources in public secondary school in Borno State, Nigeria;
2. relationship between supply of teaching learning resources on students' academic performance in public secondary school in Borno State, Nigeria;

Hypothesis

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significant;

- H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between funding and supply of teaching learning resources in public secondary school in Borno State, Nigeria;
- H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between supply of teaching learning resources on students' academic performance in public secondary school in Borno State, Nigeria.

Literature Review

Joseph, Olorunkanmi, Olukemi, Adedoyin, Nweke-Love and Tunde (2021) Challenges in Nigeria's education sector and the movement of Nigerian postgraduate students to South African universities. This study found that the decision to migrate and pursue postgraduate student abroad is informed by the discouragement and frustration suffered in attaining postgraduate education in Nigeria. The study also found that many Nigerian postgraduate migrant students that desired to stay back in South Africa after the programme were discouraged from doing so because of

the frequent hostilities between the bulging South African youths. Their hostility is associated with the shrinking capacity of the host government (South Africa) to create new jobs for them

Simiyu, Abenga and Simiyu (2020) examined the implications of funding practices on adequacy of teaching learning materials and learners academic achievement in public secondary schools in kenya. The study found out that funding practices had a moderate and high association with the provision of adequate teaching learning resources. It also established that utilisation of the teaching learning resources had a moderate and high association with learners' academic achievement. The perceived has further revealed that funding level had direct association with learners' academic achievement.

A research on the relationship between funding and academic achievement has revealed that schools with a higher revenue base performed better than those whose income was low (Kurgat, 2014). This means that a school with a strong economic base and enough resources is capable of providing facilities for curriculum implementation. World Bank (2018), asserts that, as much as educational resources are necessary, they may not be sufficient to produce higher levels of student learning especially in excessive large classes of more than 60 students. Adequate and proper allocation of funds greatly influences the success of curriculum implementation process, (Usman, 2016).

Rowell and Money (2018) financing Education in Nigeria: Implications and Options for National Development. the study has found that, in the last decades, education sector has witnessed a gradual degradation in infrastructure, in manpower development and access to qualitative education. Specifically, the federal government spending on education is

below 10 percent of its overall budget.

Munge, Kimani & Ngugi (2016) this study evaluated the factors influencing financial management in public Secondary Schools in Nakuru County. The study established that budget management and financial controls positively and significantly influenced financial management.

Junge, Bosire and Kamau (2014) analyzed the effect of budgetary practices on performance of public secondary schools in Nakuru municipality. The 22 public secondary schools in the municipality were targeted. The study noted that budget practices such as budget control and allocation positively influenced performance of the schools. In the study, it was also noted that budget allocation and annual budget planning were important aspects that improved financial management in organizations in the public sector. Research conducted in the former Rift Valley province revealed that schools equipped with adequate and relevant learning resources performed better in National examinations than schools with inadequate learning resources (Kurgat, 2014). This implies that resource shortage hinders instruction and therefore lower student performance. Facilities such as effective school Libraries provide additional reading opportunities for students which in turn improve their reading skills, comprehension, writing and clarity of expression hence enhancing their performance in all other curriculum subjects. Books provide the basis for what is taught in the classroom and how

teaching is done (GPE 2014).

Methodology

The study used correlational research design. The target population for this study was 17,229 teachers. Simple random sampling techniques was used to sample 387 teachers in senior public secondary schools in Borno State, Nigeria in line with (Research Advisor, 2006). The study used questionnaire and proforma as an instruments for data collection. The questionnaire was created using a 5-point Likert scale. A questionnaire called Questionnaire on Funding Teaching Learning Materials and Students' Academic Performance (QFTLMSAP) was created for teachers. The tool used a 5-point rating scale to provide unambiguous alternatives. There were 5 Strongly Agrees (SD), 4 Agrees (A), 3 Undecideds (UD), 2 Disagrees (D), and 1 Strongly Disagree. The Cronbach Alpha technique was used to assess the questionnaire's reliability. The instrument was reliable, as evidenced by an internal consistency estimate of 0.87. A Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was employed to determine the relationship between the variables.

Data Analysis and Results

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between funding and supply of teaching learning resources in public secondary school in Borno State, Nigeria;

Table 1.1: Correlational Analysis between Funding and Students' Academic Performance in public secondary school in Borno State, Nigeria

Variable	N	Mean	SD	df	R	p-value	Remark
Funding	387	112.00	64.5187	386	0.573	0.000	Rejected
Supply of Teaching-Learning Materials	387	38.70	14.710				

Table 1 revealed that, there was statistically significant relationship between funding and supply of teaching learning resources with Pearson Product Moment Correlation $r = 0.573$. The table also revealed that, the association between funding and Supply of Teaching-Learning Materials was statistically significant since the p-value (0.000) is less than the level of

significant 0.05. Hence, there is significant relationship between funding and Supply of Teaching-Learning Materials in in public secondary school in Borno State, Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between teaching learning resources on students' academic performance in public secondary school in Borno State, Nigeria.

Table 2.0: Correlational Analysis of Supply of Teaching-Learning Materials and Sstudents' Academic Achievement in North-East, Colleges of Education.

Variable	N	Mean	SD	df	R	p-value	Remark
Supply of Teaching-Learning Materials	387	38.70	14.71	386	0.227	0.001	Rejected
Students Academic Performance	387	20.87	7.363				

Table 2 revealed that, there was no statistically significant relationship between Supply of Educational Resources and Student Academic Achievement with Pearson Product Moment Correlation $r = 0.227$. The table also revealed that, the association among Supply of Educational Resources and Student Academic Achievement was statistically not important since the p-value (0.001) is low than the level of significant 0.05. Hence, the assumption was rejected and conclude that, supply of teaching-learning materials has statistically significant relationship with students' academic performance in public secondary school in Borno State.

students' academic performance in Borno State, Nigeria.

Recommendation

Based on the research findings, the following recommendations were made:

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, the researchers conclude that funding and the availability of teaching learning materials play an important role in senior secondary school students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Borno State, Nigeria. Hence, funding and the availability of teaching - learning materials are the determinants of

1. Government and non – governmental organization should sustain the provision of fund and supply of teaching – learning resources to public secondary school in Borno State since it's established to significantly related to students' academic performance.
2. Government should also ensure the supply of teaching learning resources since it is significantly related to students' academic performance in Borno State, Nigeria.

References

- Florence M. Iteg (2016) Financing Secondary Education in Kenya: Exploring Strategic Management. Approach for Improving Quality of Education Kenya International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management, Kenyatta University
- Joseph O. I, Olorunkanmi, M. E. R, Olukemi G. A, Adedoyin I. L, Nweke-Love C. H., & Tunde A. J., Kwame B. (2021) Challenges in Nigeria's education sector and the migration of Nigerian postgraduate students to South African universities, *Cogent Social Sciences*, 7:1, DOI: [10.1080/23311886.2021.1890897](https://doi.org/10.1080/23311886.2021.1890897)
- Munge M. Kimani N. M. and Ngugi D. G. (2016) Factors Influencing Financial Management In Public Secondary Schools In Nakuru County, Kenya International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management, Kenyatta University.
- Rowell E. U. & Money O. V. (2018) Financing Education in Nigeria: Implications and Options for National Development. *World Journal of Educational Research* · DOI: [10.22158/wjer.v5n3p227](https://doi.org/10.22158/wjer.v5n3p227)